

Experiments with GPT-4 and Bard's Vision Capabilities

Introduction:

These experiments are part of a paper accepted in the EC-TEL 2024 conference.

All experiments were performed during the last week of December 2023.

Experiments:

- [Experiment #1 - Two diagrams](#)
- [Experiment #2 - Two diagrams with an alternative prompt](#)
- [Experiment #3 - Two diagrams with another alternative prompt](#)
- [Experiment #4 - Textual description of the exercise](#)

Results Overview:

- [Here](#)
-

Experiment #1 - Two diagrams

The input was:

- the beginning of the exercise, which explains the 3 mandatory classes, as well as the Tasks' valid states.
 - Note that I actually sent to GPT a screenshot which contains both information which was given to students textually (blue background portion), as well as the diagram (white background portion).
 - the specific exercise diagram for exercise f06(), which had as goal "assigning a Task to a Worker / Employee".
-

Experiment #1.A

- **Model: GPT-4**
- **Date: 26/12/2023**

Log

- Log is pasted here because GPT-4 does not allow link sharing when the chat has images

You

I will give you two images/diagrams (A and B) which describe parts of a system which must be Implemented in Java.

Here's diagram A:

ChatGPT

ChatGPT

The image you've uploaded seems to be a diagram describing a state transition for tasks in a system. The text is in Portuguese and outlines three mandatory classes (Empresa [Company], Funcionario [Employee], Tarefa [Task]), and the states through which a task can transition (Criada [Created], Planeada [Planned], Iniciada [Started], Concluída [Concluded]). It also includes some specific details about how each state transition occurs and notes about the implementation considerations, such as using a String to represent the month, which is acknowledged as a simplification for the exercise.

If you need to implement this system in Java, you'll need to define classes that represent each entity and manage the state transitions as specified. Each task would likely have a state field that determines its current state, and methods to manage the transitions that check for validity before changing the state.

Should you have specific questions or need assistance with writing the Java code based on this diagram, feel free to ask!

You

Now here's diagram B:

ChatGPT

ChatGPT

The second diagram you've uploaded is labeled "Implemente na classe Main" and it depicts the interactions between different objects within a Java program. It details how an `Empresa` (Company) object and a `Tarefa` (Task) object are related to a `Funcionario` (Employee) object. The diagram suggests the use of a function or method represented by "f06" which seems to return a boolean value based on the status of the task and whether the employee belongs to the company.

The objects `Empresa` and `Tarefa` are shown passing information to this function, which, upon successful validation (`true`), updates the `Tarefa` object to associate it with the `Funcionario` object. The `Funcionario` object's task count `c` is incremented from `N` to `N + 1` tasks, indicating a successful assignment of the task.

Based on both diagrams A and B, it appears you're looking to create a Java system that manages tasks within a company, assigning them to employees and tracking their progression through different states.

If you need help with writing the Java code to implement this logic, please let me know how I can assist you further.

You

Give me the Java code to implement this system.

ChatGPT

ChatGPT

To implement the system described by the diagrams, you'll need several Java classes: `Empresa` to represent the company, `Funcionario` to represent the employee, `Tarefa` to represent tasks, and a `Main` class to tie everything together and execute the program. Here's a simple implementation:

java

Copy code

```
import java.util.ArrayList;
import java.util.List;

// Class representing a Company
class Empresa {
    private String nome;
    private List<Tarefa> tarefas;

    public Empresa(String nome) {
        this.nome = nome;
        this.tarefas = new ArrayList<>();
    }

    // Method to add a task to the company
    public void addTarefa(Tarefa tarefa) {
        tarefas.add(tarefa);
    }

    // Check if a task belongs to the company
    public boolean containsTarefa(Tarefa tarefa) {
        return tarefas.contains(tarefa);
    }
}
```

```
// Class representing an Employee
class Funcionario {
    private String nome;
    private Empresa empresa;
    private List<Tarefa> tarefas;

    public Funcionario(String nome, Empresa empresa) {
        this.nome = nome;
        this.empresa = empresa;
        this.tarefas = new ArrayList<>();
    }

    // Method to assign a task to this employee
    public boolean assignTarefa(Tarefa tarefa) {
        if (empresa.containsTarefa(tarefa)) {
            tarefas.add(tarefa);
            tarefa.setFuncionario(this);
            return true;
        }
        return false;
    }

    // Method to get the number of tasks assigned to this employee
    public int getTaskCount() {
        return tarefas.size();
    }
}

// Class representing a Task
class Tarefa {
    private String descricao;
    private String mes;
    private Funcionario funcionario;

    public Tarefa(String descricao, String mes) {
        this.descricao = descricao;
        this.mes = mes;
    }

    public void setFuncionario(Funcionario funcionario) {
        this.funcionario = funcionario;
    }

    public String getDescricao() {
        return descricao;
    }

    public String getMes() {
        return mes;
    }
}
```

```
// Check if the task is assigned
public boolean isAssigned() {
    return funcionario != null;
}
}

// The Main class that ties everything together
public class Main {
    public static void main(String[] args) {
        Empresa empresa = new Empresa("Empresa XYZ");
        Funcionario funcionario = new Funcionario("Zé", empresa);
        Tarefa tarefa = new Tarefa("pinturas", "Janeiro");

        empresa.addTarefa(tarefa); // Add the task to the company

        // Try to assign the task to the employee
        if (funcionario.assignTarefa(tarefa)) {
            System.out.println("Tarefa assigned to " + funcionario.getTaskCount() + " "
                + "funcionario(s).");
        } else {
            System.out.println("Failed to assign Tarefa.");
        }
    }
}
}
```

This code defines the basic structure and relationships described in your diagrams. The `Empresa` class contains a list of `Tarefa` objects. The `Funcionario` class is linked to an `Empresa` and can have multiple `Tarefa` objects assigned to it. The `Tarefa` class includes a reference to a `Funcionario` if it has been assigned. The `Main` class creates instances of these classes and demonstrates assigning a `Tarefa` to a `Funcionario`.

Please note that this code is a simplified example based on the diagrams you provided. Depending on the full requirements of your system, you may need to add more details or functionality.

You

Give me the Java code to implement function `f06()`.

ChatGPT

ChatGPT

Based on the diagrams you've provided, `f06` seems to be a function that assigns a `Tarefa` (Task) to a `Funcionario` (Employee) if the task is part of the `Empresa` (Company) and if the task is not already assigned. It returns `true` if the assignment is successful and `false` otherwise.

Given the classes I've previously defined, I'll now implement `f06` as a method within the `Funcionario` class, as it's the employee who gets assigned a task. Here's how you could implement it:

```
class Funcionario {
    private String nome;
    private Empresa empresa;
    private List<Tarefa> tarefas;

    public Funcionario(String nome, Empresa empresa) {
        this.nome = nome;
        this.empresa = empresa;
        this.tarefas = new ArrayList<>();
    }

    // Function f06 to assign a task to this employee
    public boolean f06(Tarefa tarefa) {
        // Check if the task belongs to the company and is not already assigned
        if (empresa.containsTarefa(tarefa) && !tarefa.isAssigned()) {
            tarefas.add(tarefa); // Assign the task to the employee
            tarefa.setFuncionario(this); // Set the employee as the task's owner
            return true;
        }
        return false;
    }

    // ... other methods ...
}

// The rest of the classes remain unchanged
```

In the `Main` class, you can now use the `f06` method to assign a task to an employee like this:

```
public class Main {
    public static void main(String[] args) {
        Empresa empresa = new Empresa("Empresa XYZ");
        Funcionario funcionario = new Funcionario("Zé", empresa);
        Tarefa tarefa = new Tarefa("pinturas", "Janeiro");

        empresa.addTarefa(tarefa); // Add the task to the company

        // Use f06 to assign the task to the employee
        if (funcionario.f06(tarefa)) {
            System.out.println("Tarefa assigned successfully to funcionario: " +
funcionario.getNome());
        } else {
            System.out.println("Failed to assign Tarefa.");
        }
    }
}
```

Please make sure that you have all the necessary getters/setters implemented in the `Tarefa` class and other classes if needed to support the above method. This is a simple and direct interpretation of the diagrams provided, but your actual implementation might require additional logic depending on other system requirements.

Evaluation Comments:

- Function in the wrong class
- Wrong protocol (only receiving Task)
- Not static
- Implementation is only partially correct, since it only checks if the Task is not assigned. Does not respect the transition rules.

Experiment #1.B

- Model = Google Bard

Experiments with GPT-4 and Bard's Vision Capabilities v.101

- **Date:** 26/12/2023
- **Notes:**
 - Bard replied to the prompt "Which Bard version are you?" with 4.0.0
- **Log**
 - <https://bard.google.com/share/e145052b1ac4>

User

I will give you two images/diagrams (A and B) which describe parts of a system which must be Implemented in Java. Here's diagram A:

Bard

I see. Diagram A shows the conceptual model for a system with three mandatory classes: Empresa (Company), Funcionario (Employee), and Tarefa (Task). The diagram also shows the possible states of a Task: criada (created), planeada (planned), iniciada (started), and concluída (completed).

Here is a summary of the information in the diagram:

- Classes: Empresa, Funcionario, Tarefa
- Task states: criada, planeada, iniciada, concluída
- Valid state transitions: criada -> planeada, planeada -> iniciada, iniciada -> concluída

This information can be used to implement the system in Java as follows:

- Create three Java classes to represent the Empresa, Funcionario, and Tarefa entities.
- Define an enumeration for the Task states.
- Implement the logic for transitioning between Task states.

For example, the following code shows a simple implementation of the Tarefa class:

```
public enum TaskState {
    CRIADA, PLANEADA, INICIADA, CONCLUÍDA
}

public class Tarefa {
    private Long id;
    private String descrição;
    private TaskState estado;

    public Tarefa(String descrição) {
        this.descrição = descrição;
        this.estado = TaskState.CRIADA;
    }

    public void planejar() {
        if (this.estado == TaskState.CRIADA) {
            this.estado = TaskState.PLANEADA;
        } else {
            throw new IllegalStateException("Não é possível planejar uma tarefa que não
esteja criada.");
        }
    }

    public void iniciar() {
        if (this.estado == TaskState.PLANEADA) {
            this.estado = TaskState.INICIADA;
        } else {
            throw new IllegalStateException("Não é possível iniciar uma tarefa que não
esteja planeada.");
        }
    }

    public void concluir() {
        if (this.estado == TaskState.INICIADA) {
            this.estado = TaskState.CONCLUÍDA;
        } else {
            throw new IllegalStateException("Não é possível concluir uma tarefa que não
esteja iniciada.");
        }
    }

    // getters and setters omitted for brevity
}
```

Experiments with GPT-4 and Bard's Vision Capabilities v.101

This is just a simple example, of course. The specific implementation of the system will vary depending on the specific requirements. However, the information in Diagram A can be used as a starting point for implementing the system in Java

User

Now here's diagram B:

Bard

Diagram B shows a more detailed implementation of the system described in Diagram A. It shows the following:

- The Empresa class has a list of Funcionario objects.
- The Funcionario class has a list of Tarefa objects.
- The Tarefa class has a reference to its parent Funcionario object.

This implementation allows the following:

- Empresas can manage their employees and their employees' tasks.
- Employees can view and manage their own tasks.
- Tasks can be linked to their parent employees.

This information can be used to implement the system in Java as follows:

- Add a list of Funcionario objects to the Empresa class.
- Add a list of Tarefa objects to the Funcionario class.
- Add a reference to the parent Funcionario object to the Tarefa class.

For example, the following code shows an updated implementation of the Empresa and Funcionario classes:

```
public class Empresa {
    private Long id;
    private String descrição;
    private List<Funcionario> funcionários;

    public Empresa(String descrição) {
```

```
    this.descricao = descricao;
    this.funcionarios = new ArrayList<>();
}

public void adicionarFuncionario(Funcionario funcionario) {
    this.funcionarios.add(funcionario);
}

public List<Funcionario> getFuncionarios() {
    return funcionarios;
}
}

public class Funcionario {
    private Long id;
    private String nome;
    private Empresa empresa;
    private List<Tarefa> tarefas;

    public Funcionario(String nome, Empresa empresa) {
        this.nome = nome;
        this.empresa = empresa;
        this.tarefas = new ArrayList<>();
    }

    public void adicionarTarefa(Tarefa tarefa) {
        this.tarefas.add(tarefa);
    }

    public List<Tarefa> getTarefas() {
        return tarefas;
    }
}
}
```

The Tarefa class can be updated to include a reference to the parent Funcionario object:

```
public class Tarefa {
    private Long id;
    private String descricao;
    private TaskState estado;
    private Funcionario funcionario;

    public Tarefa(String descricao, Funcionario funcionario) {
        this.descricao = descricao;
        this.estado = TaskState.CRIADA;
        this.funcionario = funcionario;
    }
}
```

```
// other methods omitted for brevity  
}
```

This implementation allows the system to satisfy the requirements of Diagram B, such as allowing empresas to manage their employees and their employees' tasks, and allowing employees to view and manage their own tasks.

I hope this summary is helpful. Please let me know if you have any other questions.

User

Give me the Java code to implement this system.

Bard

...

User

Give me the Java code to implement function f06().

Bard

I'm ready to review function f06() and provide you with the corresponding Java code. Please provide the definition of function f06() so I can generate the appropriate implementation.

User

The function f06() is described in diagram B.

Bard

Based on my understanding of diagram B, here's the Java code for function f06():

```
public List<Tarefa> obterTarefasPorEstado(Empresa empresa, TaskState estado) {  
    List<Tarefa> tarefas = new ArrayList<>();  
  
    for (Funcionario funcionario : empresa.getFuncionários()) {  
        for (Tarefa tarefa : funcionario.getTarefas()) {  
            if (tarefa.getEstado() == estado) {  
                tarefas.add(tarefa);  
            }  
        }  
    }  
}
```

```
    return tarefas;  
}
```

This code defines a function `obterTarefasPorEstado()` that takes an `Empresa` object and a `TaskState` object as parameters and returns a list of `Tarefa` objects that have the specified `estado`.

The function iterates through the list of `Funcionario` objects associated with the `Empresa` object and, for each `Funcionario`, it iterates through the list of `Tarefa` objects associated with that `Funcionario` object. If a `Tarefa` object has the specified `estado`, it is added to the list of `tarefas`.

Finally, the list of `tarefas` is returned.

Generated function:

Based on my understanding of diagram B, here's the Java code for function f06():

Java

```
public List<Tarefa> obterTarefasPorEstado(Empresa empresa, TaskState estado) {  
    List<Tarefa> tarefas = new ArrayList<>();  
  
    for (Funcionario funcionario : empresa.getFuncionários()) {  
        for (Tarefa tarefa : funcionario.getTarefas()) {  
            if (tarefa.getEstado() == estado) {  
                tarefas.add(tarefa);  
            }  
        }  
    }  
  
    return tarefas;  
}
```

Evaluation Comments:

- It didn't respect the expected protocol: it is receiving a Company and a TaskState object, instead of a Company, a Task and an Employee.
- The actual behaviour is very far from the expected one: it is returning the company's tasks that are in a certain state (input).

- It didn't respect the name f06(). However, the used name is coherent with the implemented behaviour.

- Told me to place the function in the Empresa class.

GPT-4 vs Bard:

- GPT gave us more interpretation and less code (code was only generated when it was specifically asked for), while Bard started outputting code earlier and had less explanations.
 - Bard gave us a better implementation of the Task class and of the state transition validations (bonus: the TaskState enum)
 - GPT gave a better result overall
 - It's f06() function was close to the expected behavior
 - Bard's attempt at f06() is very bad
 - The behavior is very far from the one described in the diagram
 - A solution mixing ideas from both models would actually be ideal
-

Experiment #2 - Two diagrams with an alternative prompt

Input:

- Same input as in experiment one, but with a prompt that tells GPT to consider both diagrams.

Experiment #2.A

- **Model:** GPT-4
- **Date:** 30/12/2023
- **Log** is here because GPT-4 does not allow link sharing when the chat has images

You

I will give you two images/diagrams (A and B) which describe parts of a system which must be Implemented in Java.

ChatGPT

ChatGPT

That sounds great! Please upload the images or diagrams (A and B) that describe the parts of the system you want to implement in Java. Once I have them, I'll be able to assist you further.

You

Esta ficha permite alguma variabilidade em termos de modelo de dados. No entanto, existem 3 classes obrigatórias:

- Empresa
- Funcionario
- Tarefa

Estados das Tarefas

Considere também o seguinte diagrama que apresenta os estados pelos quais uma Tarefa pode passar, nomeadamente: criada -> planeada -> iniciada -> concluída. Note que as transições de estado não indicadas são inválidas.

Nota: neste exercício vamos usar uma String para representar o mês. Num programa a sério esta escolha é bastante questionável (provavelmente usaríamos uma instância da classe Date do Java ou algo semelhante) e apenas a vamos usar neste exercício por uma questão de simplificação.

Diagram A:

ChatGPT

ChatGPT

Experiments with GPT-4 and Bard's Vision Capabilities
v.101

You've provided an image of a diagram which seems to describe a state transition system for tasks within a company, along with some text in Portuguese. It outlines that there are three mandatory classes:

- Empresa (Company)
- Funcionario (Employee)
- Tarefa (Task)

The state diagram for tasks shows that a task transitions from "Criada" (Created) to "Planeada" (Planned), then to "Iniciada" (Started), and finally to "Concluida" (Completed). Each state transition is triggered by an event, such as the month being received, an employee being assigned, or the duration being received.

The note at the bottom indicates that for simplicity in this exercise, a String will be used to represent the month. In a serious program, the choice would probably be a Date instance from Java or something similar, but it's simplified for this exercise.

Based on this information, I can help you outline the Java classes and logic to model this system. If there's a second image (B) you mentioned, please upload it as well, so I can ensure that the entire system is taken into account.

You

Diagram B:

ChatGPT

ChatGPT

Diagram B appears to provide a visual representation of the interactions between the classes `Empresa` (Company), `Funcionario` (Employee), and `Tarefa` (Task), as well as the implementation in a Java `Main` class. There's a function, possibly named `f06`, that returns a boolean value based on the current state of the task and whether the employee belongs to the company.

With both Diagram A and B, we can start outlining the classes and their relationships in Java.

You'd need to create the following classes:

`Empresa` class, which will have a list of `Funcionario` (Employee) objects and probably methods to add tasks or employees.

`Funcionario` class, which would contain details about the employee and the tasks they are assigned to.

`Tarefa` class, which represents a task and includes its state, name, and any other properties like the month it was planned or the duration if completed.

Here's a rough sketch of how these classes might be defined in Java:

```
class Empresa {
    private List<Funcionario> funcionarios;
    private List<Tarefa> tarefas;

    // Constructor, getters, setters, and methods to manipulate tasks and
    // employees.
}

class Funcionario {
    private String nome;
    private List<Tarefa> tarefas;

    // Constructor, getters, setters, and methods to manipulate tasks.
}

class Tarefa {
    private String nome;
    private String estado; // "Criada", "Planeada", "Iniciada", "Concluida"
    private String mesPlanejado; // If planned
    private int duracao; // If concluded

    // Constructor, getters, setters, and state transition methods.
}

class Main {
    public static void main(String[] args) {
        // Implementation logic as per the diagrams.
    }
}
```

For the state transitions, you can add methods in the `Tarefa` class like `planear`, `iniciar`, and `concluir`. The `Main` class would be where you instantiate your objects and simulate the transitions based on the rules provided in the diagrams.

You would also implement the `f06` function, which seems to check some condition about the task and employee.

Would you like assistance with the specifics of the class methods or the implementation details?

You

Using the two previous diagrams (A and B), give me the full Java code for this system.

ChatGPT

ChatGPT

Certainly! Based on the diagrams you provided, I'll create a simplified Java code representation of the Empresa (Company), Funcionario (Employee), and Tarefa (Task) system.

Here's a basic version of the code, encapsulating the state transitions for a Tarefa and the relationships between Empresa, Funcionario, and Tarefa:

```
import java.util.ArrayList;
import java.util.List;
import java.util.Optional;

class Empresa {
    private List<Funcionario> funcionarios = new ArrayList<>();
    private List<Tarefa> tarefas = new ArrayList<>();

    public void addFuncionario(Funcionario funcionario) {
        funcionarios.add(funcionario);
    }

    public void addTarefa(Tarefa tarefa) {
        tarefas.add(tarefa);
    }

    public boolean f06(Funcionario funcionario) {
        return funcionarios.contains(funcionario);
    }

    // Additional methods as needed
}

class Funcionario {
    private String nome;
    private List<Tarefa> tarefas = new ArrayList<>();

    public Funcionario(String nome) {
        this.nome = nome;
    }
}
```

```
public void addTarefa(Tarefa tarefa) {
    tarefas.add(tarefa);
}

public String getNome() {
    return nome;
}

// Additional methods as needed
}

class Tarefa {
    private String nome;
    private String estado;
    private String mesPlanejado;
    private int duracao;

    public Tarefa(String nome) {
        this.nome = nome;
        this.estado = "Criada";
    }

    public void planejar(String mes) {
        if ("Criada".equals(this.estado)) {
            this.mesPlanejado = mes;
            this.estado = "Planeada";
        }
    }

    public void iniciar(Funcionario funcionario) {
        if ("Planeada".equals(this.estado)) {
            funcionario.addTarefa(this);
            this.estado = "Iniciada";
        }
    }

    public void concluir(int duracao) {
        if ("Iniciada".equals(this.estado)) {
            this.duracao = duracao;
            this.estado = "Concluida";
        }
    }

    public String getNome() {
        return nome;
    }
}
```

```
public String getEstado() {
    return estado;
}

// Additional methods as needed
}

public class Main {
    public static void main(String[] args) {
        Empresa empresa = new Empresa();
        Funcionario zé = new Funcionario("Zé");
        Tarefa pinturas = new Tarefa("pinturas");

        empresa.addFuncionario(zé);
        empresa.addTarefa(pinturas);

        pinturas.planear("Janeiro");
        pinturas.iniciar(zé);
        pinturas.concluir(30);

        // Validate the state transitions and the f06 function
        System.out.println("Tarefa state: " + pinturas.getEstado());
        System.out.println("Funcionário belongs to Empresa: " + empresa.f06(zé));
    }
}
```

This code creates a company, an employee named "Zé", and a task named "pinturas". It then goes through the state transitions of the task from "created" to "planned", to "started", and finally to "completed". The `Main` class tests these transitions and prints out the final state of the task and whether the employee belongs to the company.

This is a simplified representation. In a full system, you would need to implement error checking, ensure that only valid transitions can occur, and handle other business logic as required by the system's specifications.

Evaluation Comments:

- The function was created in the wrong class (the diagram asked for this to be added to the Main class, but it was generated in the Company class)

Experiments with GPT-4 and Bard's Vision Capabilities v.101

- Has the wrong parameters: only receives an Employee instead of the 3 expected arguments.
- The function should be static (although we do not say it explicitly in the diagram, the students should be able to figure it out)
- The behaviour is very incomplete: it only checks if the Employee belongs to the Company object.

Experiment #2.B

- **Model:** Bard
- **Date:** 30/12/2023
- **Log:** <https://g.co/bard/share/4658c9b7754b>

✦ Assuming `f06()` is a function that allows a company to assign a task to an employee, the corresponding Java code would be:

```
Java

public void atribuirTarefaAEmpregado(Empresa empresa, Funcionario funcionario, Tarefa tarefa) {
    if (tarefa.getStatus() != StatusTarefa.CRIADA) {
        throw new IllegalArgumentException("A tarefa não pode ser atribuída a um funcionário se já
    }

    tarefa.setFuncionario(funcionario);
    tarefaRepository.save(tarefa);
}

Use code with caution. Learn more
```

This function first checks if the task's status is `CRIADA` (Created). If not, it throws an `IllegalArgumentException` to prevent assigning a task to an employee when it's already in another state. Otherwise, it sets the task's `funcionario` attribute to the specified `funcionario` and saves the updated task to the repository.

Comments

- Bard generated multiple extra code, such as a `TaskManagementSystem` class, 3 *interfaces* (e.e. `TaskInterface`, `CompanyInterface`)
- As for function `f06()`, it is partially correct, but has some minor issues:
 - State transition validation is incorrect: checks if task is Created instead of Planned
 - Does not check if the Employee belongs to the company
 - The argument order is incorrect
 - Expected: Company, Task, Employee
 - Got: Company, Task, Employee

- Does not return boolean (launches Exception) instead
- Not declared as Static
- The function name f06() was not respected
 - (Bard generated a better name.)
- The function was created in the wrong class:
 - `TaskManagementSystem`

Experiment #3 - Two diagrams with another alternative prompt

Input:

- Similar to experiment #1 and #2, but this time I asked the models to generate the required function in the first prompt.
 - “code for the function that is specified in diagram B”

Experiment #3.A

- Model = GPT-4
- Date: 31/12/2023
- Log: Log is pasted here because GPT-4 does not allow link sharing when the chat has images

You

I will give you two images/diagrams (A and B) which describe parts of a system which must be Implemented in Java.

I want you to give me the code for the function that is specified in diagram B.

Here's diagram A:

Esta ficha permite alguma variabilidade em termos de modelo de dados. No entanto, existem 3 classes obrigatórias:

- Empresa
- Funcionario
- Tarefa

Estados das Tarefas

Considere também o seguinte diagrama que apresenta os estados pelos quais uma Tarefa pode passar, nomeadamente: criada -> planeada -> iniciada -> concluída. Note que as transições de estado não indicadas são inválidas.

Nota: neste exercício vamos usar uma String para representar o mês. Num programa a sério esta escolha é bastante questionável (provavelmente usaríamos uma instância da classe Date do Java ou algo semelhante) e apenas a vamos usar neste exercício por uma questão de simplificação.

ChatGPT

ChatGPT

The image you've uploaded appears to be diagram A, which likely contains information needed to understand the context for diagram B. However, since I need diagram B to provide the specific function code you're asking for, could you please upload diagram B as well? Once you provide the second diagram, I'll be able to help you with the Java implementation for the function it specifies.

You

Now here's diagram B:

ChatGPT

ChatGPT

The diagram B you've provided seems to illustrate a flow or a function within a Java system that involves objects from a class `Empresa` (Company), `Tarefa` (Task), and `Funcionario` (Employee).

The function, labeled `f06`, takes in these objects and returns a boolean value. The return value is dependent on the current state of the task and whether the employee belongs to the company.

Based on this diagram, here's a Java function that could represent `f06`. Note that without more context or class definitions, I have to make assumptions about the methods and fields that exist on `Empresa`, `Tarefa`, and `Funcionario`.

```
public class Main {  
  
    // Assuming Empresa, Tarefa, and Funcionario are classes defined elsewhere  
    // with the necessary fields like descricao, mes, nome, etc.  
  
    public static void main(String[] args) {  
        // Example instantiation, the actual objects would come from your program's  
        // logic  
        Empresa empresa = new Empresa(); // Details would need to be filled out  
        Tarefa tarefa = new Tarefa("pinturas", "Janeiro"); // Assuming constructor  
        Tarefa(descricao, mes)  
    }  
}
```

Experiments with GPT-4 and Bard's Vision Capabilities
v.101

```
Funcionario funcionario = new Funcionario("Zé"); // Assuming constructor
Funcionario(nome)

// ... Rest of your main logic
}

// f06 function as described in the diagram
public static boolean f06(Empresa empresa, Tarefa tarefa, Funcionario
funcionario) {
// Assuming there are methods like tarefa.getDescricao(), tarefa.getMes() and
// empresa.containsFuncionario(funcionario) that check if the employee belongs
to the company
// The actual implementation of these methods would depend on the Empresa,
Tarefa, and Funcionario classes
return tarefa.getDescricao().equals("pinturas") &&
tarefa.getMes().equals("Janeiro") &&
empresa.containsFuncionario(funcionario);
}
}

// Classes (placeholders based on the given diagram)
class Empresa {
// ... fields and methods

public boolean containsFuncionario(Funcionario funcionario) {
// ... method implementation
return false; // Placeholder
}
}

class Tarefa {
private String descricao;
private String mes;

public Tarefa(String descricao, String mes) {
this.descricao = descricao;
this.mes = mes;
}

// ... other fields and methods

public String getDescricao() {
return descricao;
}

public String getMes() {
return mes;
}
}
```

```
class Funcionario {  
    private String nome;  
  
    public Funcionario(String nome) {  
        this.nome = nome;  
    }  
  
    // ... other fields and methods  
  
    public String getNome() {  
        return nome;  
    }  
}
```

Please replace the ... with the actual logic, fields, and methods based on your specific requirements and class definitions. The `f06` function assumes that the `Empresa` class has a method to check if a `Funcionario` is part of the company (`containsFuncionario`), and that the `Tarefa` class has methods to get its description and month (`getDescricao` and `getMes`). The return statement checks if the task description and month match specific values and if the employee is part of the company. Adjust the logic as needed for your actual implementation.

Generated function:

```
// f06 function as described in the diagram  
public static boolean f06(Empresa empresa, Tarefa tarefa, Funcionario  
funcionario) {  
    // Assuming there are methods like tarefa.getDescricao(), tarefa.getMes() and  
    // empresa.containsFuncionario(funcionario) that check if the employee belongs  
    // to the company  
    // The actual implementation of these methods would depend on the Empresa,  
    // Tarefa, and Funcionario classes  
    return tarefa.getDescricao().equals("pinturas") &&  
        tarefa.getMes().equals("Janeiro") &&  
        empresa.containsFuncionario(funcionario);  
}
```

Evaluation Comments:

- The function is in the correct class (Main)
- It is static as expected

- However, the logic is hardcoded to the diagram B's example data and will not work with other test cases

Experiment #3.B

- Model = GPT-4
- Date: 31/12/2023
- Log: <https://g.co/bard/share/b71017749b54>

Generated function:

```
public boolean isTarefaConcluida(Tarefa tarefa, Funcionario funcionario) {  
    // Retorna verdadeiro se a tarefa estiver concluída e o funcionário pertencer à empresa  
    return tarefa.isConcluida() && funcionarios.contains(funcionario);  
}
```

Evaluation Comments:

- The function was created in the Company class (should be in Main)
- The function's protocol is incorrect (only receives Task and Employee)
- Not declared a static
- The behaviour is incorrect: the function is returning true when the task is Finished and the employee belongs to the company.
 - This is wrong because the relevant status to be able to assign the employee is Planned and not Finished
 - It also does not associate the Employee with the Task

Experiment #4 - Textual description of the exercise

The input was the following text, which is a “translation” of the two images supplied in the “vision” experiments:

- Create in your Main class a Java function called f06() which must receive 3 parameters: a Company object, a Task object, and an Employee object. This function must associate the Worker with the Task. However, the association can only be performed if the Task's state transition is valid and if the Worker belongs to the company. If the association is performed the function must return true. Otherwise, the function must return false.
- The valid Task's valid states are:
 - In the Created state, the Task only has a Description
 - In the Planned state, the Task has a Description and a Month
 - In the Started state, the Task has a Description, a Month and an Employee
 - In the Finished state, the Task has a Description, a Month, an Employee, and its Duration
- The valid Task transitions are the following: created -> planned -> started (receives Employee) -> finished.

Experiment #4.A

- Model: GPT-4
- Date = 31/12/2023
- Log: <https://chat.openai.com/share/5d61d909-cdd2-4bf1-9e7b-9a0f03a107ab>

Generated function:

```
public boolean f06(Company company, Task task, Employee employee) {  
    // Check if the employee belongs to the company  
    if (!company.isEmployee(employee)) {  
        return false;  
    }  
  
    // Check if the task state transition is valid  
    if (!task.isValidStateTransition(Task.State.STARTED)) {  
        return false;  
    }  
  
    // Associate the task with the employee  
    task.setEmployee(employee);  
    task.setState(Task.State.STARTED);  
    return true;  
}
```

Evaluation Comments:

- GPT-4 generated mostly correct code in the first reply.
- Correct class (Main), as expected due to textual prompt
- The only mistake in the f06() function was that it did not include the static keyword

Experiment #4.B

- Model: Bard
- Date = 31/12/2023
- Log: <https://g.co/bard/share/56bd8b9e4d05>

Generated function:

Java

```
public static boolean f06(Company company, Task task, Employee employee) {
    if (task.getState() == TaskState.CREATED) {
        task.setState(TaskState.PLANNED);
        task.setMonth(LocalDate.now().getMonth());
    } else if (task.getState() == TaskState.PLANNED && employee.getCompany().equals(company)) {
        task.setEmployee(employee);
        task.setState(TaskState.STARTED);
    } else if (task.getState() == TaskState.STARTED) {
        task.setDuration(Duration.between(task.getStartDate(), LocalDate.now()));
        task.setState(TaskState.FINISHED);
    } else {
        return false;
    }
    return true;
}
```

Evaluation Comments:

- The function's **protocol** is correct (including the static portion)
- Bard more or less misunderstood the function's goal
- It created the function in such a way that it can perform multiple state-transitions
- The portion related with the requested behavior is correct (see the following image)
- However, it will return true in situations where it should not.

Experimental Results Overview

This evaluation was done focusing on the generated function, which was the goal of the diagram. Mistakes in “auxiliary” code (e.g. Employee class) were ignored.

The following six evaluation criteria were used:

- Class: the function was generated in the correct class (i.e. Main)
- Protocol: the function was created with the expected protocol
 - receiving 3 arguments: Company, Task, Employee
 - returning boolean
- Static: the generated function is static
 - (this could be merged with protocol, but I splitted them for now)
- Behaviour (or Logic)
 - B1 - Task transition status validation
 - B2 - Checks if the employee belongs to the Company
 - B3 - Associates Task with Employee

Note: both models sometimes changed the function name. That was not included in the evaluation “grid”.

Experiment	GPT-4	Bard
#1 (diagram)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - class ✗ - protocol ✗(only receiving Task) - static ✗ - behavior B1 - ✗ - behavior B2 - ✗ - behavior B3 - ✓ <p>Notes: Implementation is only partially correct, since it checks if the Task is not assigned instead of checking if it is planned. Does not respect the transition rules. It also checks if the Task belongs to the Company instead of testing if the Employee belongs to the company.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - class ✗ - protocol ✗ receives a Company and a TaskState object, instead of a Company, a Task and an Employee. - static ✗ - behavior B1 - ✗ - behavior B2 - ✗ - behavior B3 - ✗ <p>Notes: The actual behavior is very far from the expected one: it is returning the company's tasks that are in a certain state (input). It didn't respect the name f06(). However, the used name is coherent with the implemented behavior.</p>
#2 (diagram)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - class ✗ (placed in the Company class) - protocol ✗(only receives an Employee obj instead of the 3 expected arguments). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - class ✗(created in a new class <code>TaskManagementSystem</code>) - protocol ✗ (argument order is incorrect ; also, does not return boolean and launches exception instead)

Experiments with GPT-4 and Bard's Vision Capabilities
v.101

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - static ❌ - behavior B1 - ❌ - behaviour B2 - ✅ - behaviour B3 - ❌ <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The behavior is very incomplete: it only checks if the Employee belongs to the Company object. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - static ❌ - behavior B1 - ❌ - behaviour B2 - ❌ - behaviour B3 - ✅ <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - State transition validation is incorrect: checks if task is Created instead of Planned - Does not check if the Employee belongs to the company - The function name f06() was not respected. (Bard generated a better name.) - Overall solution with many extra components (uses interfaces)
#3 (diagram)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - class ✅(i.e. Main) - protocol ✅ - static ✅ <p>behaviour B1/B2/B3: ❌</p> <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the logic is hardcoded to respect the diagram B's example data and will not work with other test cases 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - class ❌(Company) - protocol ❌(only 2 args) - static ❌ - behavior B1/B2/B3 - ❌ <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Behaviour is incomplete (does not assign Task<->Employee) and State Validation Logic is incorrect
#4 (textual)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - class ✅ - protocol ✅ - static ❌ - behavior B1/B2/B3 ✅ <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - GPT-4 generated mostly correct code in the first reply. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - class ✅ - protocol ✅ - static ✅ - behavior B1: ✅❌ (see notes) - behavior B2: ✅❌ (see notes) - behavior B3: ✅❌ (see notes) <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bard more or less misunderstood the function's goal: the generated function

Experiments with GPT-4 and Bard's Vision Capabilities
v.101

	<p>- The only mistake in the f06() function was that it did not include the static keyword</p>	<p>can perform multiple state-transitions. The portion related with the requested behavior is correct. However, it will return true in situations where it should not ! .</p> <p>- As such, we assigned 50% of the "points" in each sub-behaviour.</p>
--	--	--

Correctness score for each experiment

This is based on the correctness of 6 evaluation items.

(logic = behaviour implementations)

	Experiment 1 (diagram)	Experiment 2 (diagram)	Experiment 3 (diagram)	Experiment 4 (textual)
GPT-4	1/6 compilation: 0/3 logic: 1/3	1/6 compilation: 0/3 logic: 1/3	3/6 compilation: 3/3 logic: 0/3	5/6 compilation: 2/3 logic: 3/3
Bard	0/6 compilation: 0/3 logic: 0/3	1/6 compilation: 0/3 logic: 1/3	0/6 compilation: 0/3 logic: 0/3	4.5/6 compilation: 3/3 logic: 1.5/3

Notes:

- With diagrams, in 2 of the 3 experiments, the instruction "Implement in class Main" was not respected
- The same is true for the static (it was not written ; inference was needed)
- Exception for both issues: GPT-4 in Experiment #3